

Characterization and Application of ZnFe_2O_4 Soft Ferrite: A Review

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ABSTRACT:

Zinc ferrite (ZnFe_2O_4) is a member of the spinel oxide family that is technologically important and has attracted great attention due to the unique combination of its magnetic, electrical, and thermal properties. This review paper describes the structure, synthesis methods, and the use of zinc ferrite. More specifically, it highlights the experimental factors, cation distribution, and property dependencies. Some of the synthesis techniques mentioned briefly is solid state, sol-gel, hydrothermal, plasma-assisted, and green methods. The major aspects of comparison for ZnFe_2O_4 obtained with these different methods are their crystallinity, particle size, and magnetic properties. A comparison of bulk and nanostructured ZnFe_2O_4 is made, and this clarifies the much better stability and low-loss nature of bulk materials for use at high frequency and high temperature, which is perfect over and above the nanostructured ones that are getting more surface activity. Besides, the major industrial applications of magnetic cores, electromagnetic interference shielding, gas sensing, catalysis, and ceramics are thoroughly discussed from a critical point of view. Finally, the review paper points out the present research shortcomings and future trends that will lead to the creation of modern ZnFe_2O_4 -based materials.

Keywords: Ferrites, Spinel Structure, Zinc Ferrites, Magnetic Properties, Synthesis Methods.

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INTRODUCTION

The word "ferrite" comes from the Latin word ferrum which means iron, underlining iron as the central element in these materials. Ferrites are a key group of magnetic oxides where the main cations in their structure are ferric ions (Fe^{+3}) [1]. Actually, materials containing ferrites have been known since prehistoric times; magnetite (Fe_2O_3), for example, was employed as a compass material in China even more than two thousand years ago [2]. Ferrites have a unique mix of electrical and magnetic features, such as moderate saturation magnetization, high electrical resistivity, low eddy current losses, and chemical inertness [3].

Besides having lower saturation magnetization compared to pure magnetic metals and alloys, ferrites have a few very attractive qualities that can be used to advantage. For example, their

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operability at very high frequencies, getting almost no corrosion or deterioration under normal use conditions with little or no maintenance, and their making the most of the cost factor by production at large scale [4-5]. These attributes enable them to be used very effectively in a wide range of applications, including electronics, telecommunications, medical devices, and military technology [6]. Chemical composition, doping type, and production methods greatly affect the physical and chemical characteristics of the ferrites [7]. The structure of the ferrites is made of ions arranged tightly in a pattern dominated by oxygen ions, which explains their mechanical hardness and brittleness [8].

From the electrical point of view, these materials have very low conductivity and relatively high dielectric constants; the latter can be as high as thousands at low frequencies and drops to roughly 10-20 in the microwave region [9]. Their black or gray color is typically due to electronic transitions occurring between 3d and 4s energy levels. This resulted in absorption in the visible region [10]. Ferrites are magnetically characterized by features such as magnetic anisotropy and clear hysteresis loops, which might be narrow or square depending on their composition and structure [11]. Generally, ferrites can be divided into spinel garnet, hexaferrite, and orthoferrite types according to their crystalline structure, chemical composition, and magnetic properties [12]. Besides this, they can also be divided into soft and hard magnetic materials [13]. Soft ferrites have very low coercivity (≤ 40 A/m), high permeability, low magnetic losses, and relatively high saturation magnetization, making them ideal for application such as transformers, motor, inductors, and several energy conversion devices [14]. On the other hand, hard ferrites that show very high coercivity are mainly used as permanent magnets and are therefore sold under various trade names such as Ferroxdure, Koerox, Roboxid, and Magnadure [15]. Besides soft ferrites, spinel and garnet are the two structures that have been investigated to the most extent. The spinel structure, first elucidated by William Henry Bragg in 1915 [16], originates from the mineral $MgAl_2O_4$ and is typically expressed using the following general formula: MFe_2O_4 (or $MO \cdot Fe_2O_3$), where M denotes to the divalent metal ion such as, Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , or Zn^{2+} [17-18]. This structural versatility enables significant adjustment of the magnetic and electrical properties of ferrites, which is essential for tailoring them to specific technological applications [19].

PHYSICOCHEMICAL, AND CHEMICAL, STRUCTURAL CLASSIFICATION OF FERRITE NANOPARTICLES

Based on their magnetic response, ferrites are divided into two general subcategories, the first one is the hard ferrites, and the second one is the soft ferrites [20]. The main magnetic differences between these two classes of ferrites are highlighted in Table 1, and Fig. 1.

Table 1. Main Magnetic Differences between Hard Ferrites and Soft Ferrites

Property	Hard Ferrites	Soft Ferrites
Definition	Permanent magnetic materials	Temporary magnetic materials
Coercivity (Hc)	High (up to ~380 Oe)	Very low (≤ 40 A/m)
Saturation Magnetization (Ms)	High and stable	Moderate to high
Magnetic Permeability (μ)	Low	High
Curie Temperature	High	High
Magnetization Retention	Retains magnetization (permanent)	Doesn't retain magnetization
Magnetic Losses	Relatively higher	Very low
Electrical Resistivity	Good	Very high (ceramic insulators)
Crystal Structure	Hexagonal ($P6_3/mmc$)	Spinel cubic (Fd3m)
Typical Composition	Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , or Pb^{2+} with Fe^{3+}	MFe_2O_4 (e.g., Ni, Zn, Mn)
Magnetic Anisotropy	High (strong anisotropy)	Low (weak anisotropy)
Main Applications	Permanent magnets, sensors, data storage	Transformers, inductors, memory devices

$ZnFe_2O_4$ crystallises in a cubic spinel structure (Fd3m), in which Zn^{2+} ions occupy tetrahedral (A) sites and Fe^{3+} ions occupy octahedral (B) sites in the standard configuration. However, depending on the synthesis conditions, partial inversion may occur, leading to the redistribution of cations [21]. When soft and hard ferrites are exposed to a magnetic field (H), soft ferrites do not maintain a high

residual magnetic flux density (B_r) and exhibit a low coercive field (H_c) characterized by a narrow B-H curve [22,23]. Hard ferrites, on the other hand, exhibit a higher coercive field (H_c) and can maintain a high residual magnetic flux density (B_r) [24], as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Magnetic Hysteresis Loops and B-H Curves of Soft-Magnetic and Hard-Magnetic Materials
Source: [25]

TYPES OF FERRITE ACCORDING TO THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND CRYSTAL STRUCTURE

Spinal Ferrite

Spinal ferrites are a class of metal oxide characterized by a cubic structure and generally classified as magnetic materials due to their low coercivity and relatively high magnetization [26, 27]. Their crystal lattice consists of two distinct interstitial sites: tetrahedral (A-sites) and octahedral (B-sites), giving rise to general chemical formula AB_2O_4 , where A and B represented divalent and trivalent metal cations, respectively [28]. Among the commonly studied normal spinel ferrites is $ZnFe_2O_4$. Structurally, spinal ferrites can exist in two main configurations, namely normal spinel and inverse spinel structure, which are determined by the distribution of cations among the available tetrahedral and octahedral lattice sites [29, 30]. The spinel ferrite unit cell is constructed of a close-packed face-centred cubic (FCC) arrangement of oxygen ions. In the normal spinel structure, Zn^{2+} ions occupy the tetrahedral A-sites, whereas Fe^{3+} ions fill the octahedral B-sites [31]. In contrast, in the inverse spinel structure, Fe^{3+} ions occupy the tetrahedral A-sites, whereas the octahedral B-sites are equally filled by both Zn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions [32]. $ZnFe_2O_4$ shows strong magnetism thanks to spin exchange forces, which shift based on how it's made M_s values differ across methods [33]. Particle size matters too: smaller grains trigger cation inversion, flipping the crystal structure from normal to inverse spinal. This structural change directly affects magnetic behavior. Still, exact responses aren't fully predictable for now [34]. Respectively, with other ferrites, $ZnFe_2O_4$ has lower magnetic properties [35]. Additionally, The $ZnFe_2O_4$ nanoparticles (NPs) have a direct band gap between (1.80 to 3.00 eV), which makes them suitable for optical applications [36].

Hexagonal Ferrite

Hexagonal ferrites with a magneto plumbite structure are commonly represented by the general formula $MeFe_{12}O_{19}$, where Me denotes a divalent metal cation such as Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , or Ca^{2+} [37]. In contrast to cubic systems, this structure exhibits strong uniaxial anisotropy, with the c-axis as the easy axis of magnetization, while the a-axis represents the hard direction. This anisotropic behavior stabilizes the magnetic moments along the c-axis, which is a key factor behind their effectiveness as permanent magnetic materials and their relatively high ferromagnetic resonance (FMR)

frequencies. Structurally, the magneto plumbite unit cell is composed of alternating S and R blocks formed by layers of oxygen anions [38]. The S block resembles the spinel structure, containing both tetrahedral and octahedral interstitial sites occupied by Fe^{3+} ions [39]. In contrast, the R block consists of oxygen layers hosting larger divalent cations coordinated with oxygen in a different local environment, as shown in Fig. 3. This unique structural arrangement, combined with strong magneto crystalline anisotropy, provides hexagonal ferrites with excellent magnetic stability and performance [40]. Consequently, they are widely used in permanent magnets, high-frequency microwave devices, magnetic recording systems, pigments, and certain biomedical applications [41].

Figure 2. Schematic Representation of the Crystal Structure of Spinel Ferrites
Source: [25]

Figure 3. Schematic Representations of Hexagonal Ferrite Structures
Source: [25]

Garnet Ferrite

Garnet ferrites are generally described by the chemical formula $\text{Me}_3\text{Fe}_5\text{O}_{12}$, where Me represents trivalent cations such as Y^{+3} or other rare-earth ions like Ga^{+3} and Sm^{+3} . All cations in this structure exist in the trivalent state. Garnet ferrites possess a cubic crystal structure, and the distribution of cations within the lattice is relatively complex compared to other ferrite system. In a typical unit cell, 24 Me^{+3} ions occupy the dodecahedral sites, while Fe^{+3} ions distribute between 24 tetrahedral sites and 16 octahedral sites, as illustrated in Fig.4. These materials exhibit telecommunications, and data storage systems. [42, 43].

Figure 4. Schematic Representations of Garnet Ferrite Structures
Source: [25]

SYNTHESIS OF SOFT ZN FERRITE NANOPARTICLES

The synthesis of ferrite nanoparticles involves several methods: physical, chemical, thermal, and biological methods, as shown in Fig. 5, Table 2, each tailored to achieve specific particle sizes, shapes, and magnetic properties. The comprehension of these methods is crucial for optimizing the performance and functionality of ferrites in their respective applications [44]. This method includes:

Ball-Milling Method

This method is a widely used technique based on ball milling that helps reduce the particles size with high energy, thus modifying the surface properties of the materials. The particles size depends on the grinding time and the initial ball to powder ratio. This method requires a long production times and high energy. The nanoparticles obtained from this method are spherical in shape and exhibit a super paramagnetic behavior [45].

Sol Gel Method

The sol-gel technique is a chemical approach used to produce solid particles from colloidal solution through hydrolysis and subsequent polymerization, leading to gradual transition from liquid phase into a gel. This method is well known for yielding materials with high purity and uniform composition while operating under relatively mild temperature conditions. In addition, it enables the design of multifunctional materials with precise control over their nano-structural features. Among its main advantages are the use of low-cost precursors, reduce energy requirements, and a straightforward preparation process. Furthermore, the sol-gel route provides effective control over key parameters such as particle composition, homogeneity, spatial distribution and size, making it a widely preferred technique in advanced material synthesis [46, 47].

Plasma-Assist Method

The plasma reduction and production technique is a highly innovative and environmentally friendly procedure for making spinel ferrites. The nanoparticles obtained have all the attributes of excellent catalysts and medical applications. Such as high surface area, unique oxygen vacancies, and narrow size (5-25) nm. The highly reactive plasma species make the synthesis process finish in a few minutes. Green plasma synthesis at room temperature preserves the nanostructure and avoids undesired grain growth. The ferrites treated by plasma usually have a high number of surface defects and active sites that greatly enhance their performance in photo-catalysis and bactericidal application [48-50].

Hydrothermal Method

Among various synthesis procedures, the hydrothermal technique is likely the most effective one in manufacturing ferrite nanoparticle in large scale. Soluble salts containing divalent and trivalent transition metals are dissolved separately and then combined in 1:2 molar ratio, by selecting appropriate solvent mixture and varying temperature, pressure, and reaction time, nano-ferrites with well-defined size and morphologies can be obtained [51, 52].

Solid State Reaction

The solid state reaction technique is a simple and effective route to synthesis nanoparticles. In this technique, atoms or ions interact by diffusing each other at high temperature (commonly above 800°C). This method is ideal for mass production of high- purity spinel ferrite nanoparticles. The disadvantages of this method are that the reaction time is usually longer than that of other synthesis method [53,54].

Green Synthesis

The green synthesis of Spinel Ferrite has emerged as a sustainable and eco-friendly. This biogenic approach uses natural extracts-derived from plant leaves, fruits, or microorganisms-that act as both reducing and stabilizing agents. This method avoids the use of toxic solvents and high-pressure environments, resulting in biocompatibility. Consequently, green-synthesized zinc ferrites are highly sought after for sensitive applications, such as targeted drug delivery and visible-light photo-catalysis. Advantages of the Green Synthesis Method: Eco-Friendliness, Cost Effectiveness,

Biocompatibility. Energy Efficiency: The reactions typically occur at low temperatures (25–80 °C), and narrow size distribution (15–45 nm) [55-57]. The key characteristics of the synthesis methods are summarized in Table 2, and illustrated in Figure. 5.

Table 2. An Overview of Synthesis Methods Employed for Zink Ferrite Preparation

Method	Size nm	Temp °C	Key Features
Green synthesis	15-35	25-60	Eco-friendly, variable size control
Solid state reaction	>100	800-1200	High crystallinity, energy intensive
Plasma assist	5-25	RT	High purity, rapid synthesis
Ball milling	20-60	RT	Scalable, defect formation
Sol-gel	5-40	200-600	High homogeneity, good control
hydrothermal	10-80	150–250	Controlled morphology, high pressure

Figure 5. Schematic Overview of Synthesis Methods Employed for Zink Ferrite Preparation
Source: [44-57]

INDUSTRIAL AND TECHNICAL APPLICATIONS OF ZINC FERRITE ($ZnFe_2O_4$)

The spinel zinc ferrite, due to its thermodynamic stability, high electrical resistivity, and soft magnetic properties, finds its usage in several industrial fields [58]:

High-Frequency Magnetic Components

$ZnFe_2O_4$ is one of the most highly used functional materials in producing magnetic cores for transformers, inductors, and choke coils. The material's natural high electrical resistivity is a key feature in reducing eddy current losses at high frequencies. Besides that, the bulk spinel has a low coercivity (H_c) [59].

Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) Shielding and Microwave Devices

$ZnFe_2O_4$ is a perfect and powerful medium for microwave absorption because of the synergy of its dielectric properties and magnetic permeability. It is normally used in ceramic-based composites for EMI shielding. Its excellent thermal stability makes it capable to maintain the performance of electronic circuits even under conditions of high thermal or electromagnetic stress [60, 61].

Refractory Ceramics and Structural Materials

Zinc ferrites used as a component in ceramic matrices mainly to enhance magnetic and electrical properties. Also, its thermo-degradation resistance makes it suitable for high-temperature refractory coatings and specialized industrial ceramics [62, 63].

Heterogeneous Catalysis and Industrial Oxidation

Zinc ferrite probably works best in oxidant-reduction reactions where stability matters. It holds up over time, resists poisoning, and stays active through long runs. In continuous chemical plants, its solid form for catalysts where lasting performance beats sharp sensitivity [64, 65].

Solid-state sensing systems

Bulk ZnFe₂O₄ has semiconducting properties, the makes it useful in chemiresistive gas sensors. When reducing gases bind to its surface, conductivity changes noticeably. Sensitivity is lower than in nano-sized version still, stability, and reproducibility in rough industrial settings are better. The material does not degrade easily under stress or extreme conditions [66].

Stable Inorganic Pigments and Corrosion-Resistant Coatings

ZnFe₂O₄ is an important inorganic pigment widely used in the paint and coating industry. The pigment's outstanding chemical stability and ability to withstand UV result in prolonged color retention and corrosion protection of structures even under harsh environmental exposure [67, 68].

CONCLUSIONS

Zinc ferrite is versatile spinel ferrite whose functional properties are strongly governed by its crystal structure and cation distribution. This review paper demonstrates that synthesis methods play a critical role tailoring microstructure, which directly influences magnetic, electrical, and optical behavior. Provide superior thermal stability, low magnetic losses, and long-term reliability, making them more suitable for high frequency and industrial applications. Despite significant progress, challenges remain in achieving precise control over cation inversion, establishing robust structure-property relationships, and developing scalable synthesis routes.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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